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Experimental testing of a floating OWC wave energy converter in a saline outdoor wave tank

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Abstract

This project extends and enhances the understanding of a 1:15 scale model of the Ocean Energy (OE) buoy floating oscillating water column wave energy devices. The testing campaign will build on previous experimental work undertaken in indoor controlled freshwater tanks and numerical modelling by analysing the performance of the OE buoy in the large outdoor saline wave tank at Ohmsett. The focus of the testing is on performance on the moorings and hull in high energy sea states from max operational conditions to survival scenarios. Key metrics such as the OE buoy's hull pressure and stability are recorded and compared with previous tests. This work yields important data for further design optimisation of the OE system. For example, in terms of improving the OE Buoy subject device, the test campaign investigates parameters related to internal pressure of the plenum chamber at various sea states, which has a direct consequence for levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of a full-scale device.

The Ohmsett facility uses salt water with an open ocean salinity of 30-33 parts per thousand (ppt) NaCl, which provides for comparison of buoyancy effects with the freshwater tanks used in earlier studies. The facility also has the benefit of multiple instruments and cameras for measuring and documenting wave conditions. The Ohmsett test tank is equipped with three movable robust bridges that can accommodate the torque and forces of a wide range of turbines and wave energy converter (WEC) equipment. Finally, the Ohmsett facility has similar wave-making facilities and tank width and depth to Ireland's National Ocean Test Facility (Lir NOTF) but is significantly longer, which may provide for a valuable comparison of results. The longer length will allow for mitigated reflection effects during wave testing. During testing, the OE Buoy was placed as close to the wave paddles as possible to attempt to get enough data to analyze before reflected waves reach the model.

Keywords: Wave Energy Conversion; Outside Test Tank; Ohmsett

1. Introduction

In a recent collaboration with TEAMER and the MaREI Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine research (the University College Cork, Ireland), the tank testing of the Ocean Energy (OE) 1:15 scale model prototype of a floating oscillating water column (OWC) wave energy converter (WEC) was conducted at Ohmsett – The National Oil Spill Response Research & Renewable Energy Test Facility in Leonardo, New Jersey. The Ohmsett facility has a 203 m length X 20 m width X 2.4 m water depth tank with a volume of 10 million liters of sea water and the capability to generate waves of up to 1 m in amplitude (Figure 1).

Figure 1 (a) View of the Ohmsett tank from the wave generator (b) 4,700 kg (10,500 lb) hydraulically driven wave generator flaps

OE is an Irish Wave Energy Developer (<https://oceanenergy.ie/>) who specialize in the development of wave energy technology. The WEC absorbs energy from ocean waves to generate green, sustainable electricity. The results from the testing of the scaled model prototype will be used to optimize the development of a much larger WEC device at a later stage.

2. Methodology

The scale model device has been in development for over a decade and has successfully been tested at the Lir National Ocean Test Facility at the University College Cork (Ireland) and École Centrale de Nantes (France). An example of a previous test set up is shown in Figure 2. The model is instrumented with several sensors for the measurement of water pressure and level at various locations on the device.

Figure 1 Previous OE Testing at 1/15th scale

Testing was carried out at the Ohmsett test facility between the 1st and 12th May 2023, to study the operational and structural performance of the OE wave energy converter model. The model device was anchored between the main bridge and the north bridge and was subjected to a mix of irregular and regular waves. Figure 3 shows the device before and after deployment in the Ohmsett wave tank. Over 40 tests were carried out in the tank for a range of different CPM and stroke values, with and without the OE device in the water. All data were acquired and stored on the Ohmsett data acquisition system.

Figure 3 (a) OE WEC model device on deck of bridge; (B) Model deployed in Ohmsett test tank

The overall testing sequence of events was based on a program of Regular waves. The device also underwent a series of static calibration and decay tests initially and was exposed to a variety of specific wave forms.

Preparation of the OE device and associated sensors, cabling and interfacing with the Ohmsett test facility's data acquisition system was carried out during the first week (1st to the 5th of May) of the test campaign. Installation of the OE device in the test tank was carried out on the 3rd of May. Initial calibration and static tests on the OE device (while positioned in the tank, Test#1 to 22) took place on the 4th and 5th of May. The actual tank testing for the OE device utilizing several different waves (test# 23 to 63) was carried out from the 5th to the 12th of May. These tank tests will be summarized in a subsequent report.

Six water pressure sensors (Keller Series 26Y piezoresistive level probes for hydrostatic pressure measurement) and three water level (resistance wire) gauges located on the OE WEC model device, were used for the measurement of both water pressure and water levels at different parts of the model. These sensors were interfaced to the Ohmsett data acquisition system, where data were acquired and stored. The sensors are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 List of sensors used on the OE buoy

Sensor Ref #	Sensor	Description/Position/Name	Type
1	Water Level Gauge	Centre	Resistance Gauge
2	Water Level Gauge	Port	Resistance Gauge
3	Water Level Gauge	Starboard	Resistance Gauge
4	Keller Pressure sensor	Plenum Starboard (CM)	4-20 mA output
5	Keller Pressure sensor	Midship Port External (CM)	4-20 mA output
6	Keller Pressure sensor	Starboard Aft External (CM)	4-20 mA output
7	Keller Pressure sensor	Plenum Port (CM)	4-20 mA output
8	Keller Pressure sensor	Port Aft External (CM)	4-20 mA output
9	Keller Pressure sensor	Starboard Midship External (CM)	4-20 mA output

The Ohmsett test facility's Data acquisition (DAQ) system consists of the following National Instruments (NI) DAQ card modules for use with NI's CompactDAQ/CompactRIO Systems.

Table 2 Ohmsett National Instruments (NI) DAQ card modules

DAQ card Module	Description	Quantity / Number of DAQ chs.
NI 9207 (781068-01)	Provides 24Bit ADC Sampling, with input ranges of ± 10.2 V or ± 21.5 mA (depending on voltage or current measurement) with sampling rates up to 500 sps.	Qty: 2 Each module provides 16 analogue input channels (8 voltage and 8 current)
NI 9219 (779781-02)	Provides 24Bit ADC Sampling, with input ranges of ± 60 V, ± 15 V, ± 4 V, ± 1 V, ± 125 mV, with sampling rates up to 100 sps.	Qty: 1 Each module provides 4 input analogue channels. A second 9219 module was available but was not completely wired up for testing.

3. Results

Initial analysis of results has been focused on the motion analysis of the OE model device, and deriving the translational and rotational degrees of freedom, using the data acquired from the IMU sensor. The Xsens IMU MTi-100 sensor comprises a tri-axial accelerometer, tri-axial gyroscope and tri-axial magnetometer, providing measurements of acceleration [m/s²], angular velocity [rads/s] and arbitrary units [a.u] for the magnetometer respectively. The IMU does not provide any information on the six degrees of freedom (Roll (θ), Pitch (ϕ), Yaw (ψ), Surge (η), Heave (ϖ), Sway (ζ)) representing the motion of the OE model device. These parameters need to be calculated based on the acquired sensor data above. An example of the derived Pitch (ϕ) and corresponding Sway (ζ) values for one of the wave tests are shown here for reference only. Examples of pitch and sway response are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Example of derived (a) Pitch response during tank testing. (b) Sway response during tank testing.

While data are still being analyzed for a significant number of individual wave conditions, Table 3 serves to show a partial listing for specific runs and the basic wave conditions associated with them.

Table 3 Partial summary of test plan of Ohmsett wave testing

Test #	Date	Approximate Time (hrs)	Wave #	Wave Generator Settings	Nominal Wave Characteristics*	Comments
23	05/05/2023	1341	Reg Wave 1	15 cpm @ 4.5-in stroke	H(avg)=6.9 cm; Period=4.3 s; $\lambda=19.1$ m	Bridge location=158.9 m (521.2 ft); Water Depth=2.62 m (130.12 ft); These parameters are constant for the duration of the test period.
24	05/05/2023	1358	Reg Wave 2	15 cpm @ 3.0-in stroke	H(avg)=5.4 cm; Period=3.3 s; $\lambda=13.8$ m	
25	05/05/2023	1411	Reg Wave 3	40 cpm @ 3.0-in stroke	N/A	This test was repeated later as Test 52 due to uncertainty regarding the wave generator setting.
26	05/05/2023	1424	Reg Wave 4	25 cpm @ 4.5-in stroke	H(avg)=13.2 cm; Period=2.2 s; $\lambda=7.2$ m	
27	05/05/2023	1439	Reg Wave 5	35 cpm @ 3.0-in stroke	H(avg)=13.7 cm; Period=1.8 s; $\lambda=5.0$ m	
28	05/05/2023	1455	Reg Wave 6	10 cpm @ 15.0-in stroke	H(avg)=13.8 cm; Period=4.5 s; $\lambda=20.2$ m	

A portion of the test plan for the wave tank testing on the OE WEC model device was altered due to limitations and difference in the capability of the Ohmsett paddle/wave generation. The Irregular spectrum waves were not undertaken due to this. Instead, the testing program was focused on regular waves and in particular waves that could cause structural damage to such a device (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Example of wave tests on OE WEC model device in test tank.

In terms of the instrumentation and data acquisition system at Ohmsett, the current DAQ system is not optimized to perform low voltage signal measurements, as required for differential measurements. This is particularly the case for sensors with low signal outputs requiring, for example, 4-wire, strain and bridge type measurement capability, which require more sensitive and specialized low noise signal conditioning and acquisition instrumentation /equipment to perform such measurements.

4. Conclusions

Testing was carried out at the Ohmsett test facility between the 1st and 12th May 2023, to study operational and structural performance of the OE wave energy converter model. The model device was anchored between two bridges and was subjected to regular waves. Over 40 tests were carried out in the tank for a range of different CPM and stroke values, with and without the OE device in the water.

The test plan for the wave tank testing on the OE WEC model device was carried out as planned. In terms of the instrumentation and data acquisition system at Ohmsett, the current DAQ system is currently not optimized to perform low voltage and low noise signal measurements, as required for low amplitude differential measurements. This requires a specialized DAQ system setup to be installed and configured to provide such sensing capabilities for future testing.

The acquired tank test data are currently being analyzed at the MaREI Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine research (the University College Cork, Ireland) and will be provided in a later report.

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